

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WHAT MATTERS MOST”

It isn't the fortune nor jewels untold,
Not glamorous jewels nor bags of gold,
For happiness is not found in mundane things,
But in hearts contentment, without pain.

What matters most is a soul at peace,
A life where ordinary wonders never fade,
The warmth of love, a gentle hug,
The laughter that time can never erase.

It's not in the race for passing recognition,
Nor chasing the world's unending game,
True happiness blooms where love is sown,
In quiet moments we call our own.

So seek not the mundane, the shallow, the vain,
For life's gracious gifts are simple and plain,
When hearts are content and free,
That is what matters most forever.

